

A STUDY ON CUSTOMER LEVEL OF SATISFACTION TOWARDS E-BANKING SERVICES, IN TIRUNELVELI

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Abstract: Banking has moved toward a long mode from the time of ledger cards and other instruction manual substantial systems. Nowadays the majority of the Banks have electronic systems to switch their daily huge tasks of informational repossession, processing, and storage. E-banking refers to the efficient operation by the banks, It enables the spectacular lowering of operation costs and the formation of new methods of banking opportunity and its deal with the barriers of time and remoteness. E-banking is an influential value additional tool its create a center of attention to new customers and keep hold of the accessible ones. An endeavor has been completed in this paper to analyze customers' level of satisfaction towards E-banking services in Tirunelveli Banks.

Keywords: E banking, Customer satisfaction

Introduction

Technology in the Indian banking sector has evolved significantly from the days of turnaround office automation to today's online, centralized and incorporated solutions. Information technology has to turn into an essential tool in today's sector. It is growing in performance a major role in improving the services in the banking industry. Banking is now no longer restricted to the branches where one has to move toward the branch in person, to take out cash or deposit a cheque or ask for a report of accounts. With the extension of internet usage, e-banking has become one of the main revolutionary mechanisms of today's economic enlargement. Moreover, it helps in eliminating costly paper conduct and banker communication in the more and more aggressive banking surroundings. The potential aggressive gain of e-banking lies in the areas of cost decrease and satisfaction of consumer requirements.

E-Banking

E-banking is conducted by one's banking or bank account online in the course of a computer and an internet link. "Electronic banking is the utilize of a computer to recover and procedure banking data and to commence payment and transfer dealings. In a straight line with a bank or other monetary services supplier slightly via a telecommunications network

Electronic banking is a new business that allows people to work together with their banking accounts via the Internet from nearly wherever in the world. The electronic banking organization permits consumers to accurately enter their banking accounts, appraisal most modern dealings, request a present statement, transfer funds, view current bank rates and products in sequence, and reorganize checks. The electronic banking sector is able to be seen as an “extension of accessible banks.”

Statement of the Problem

The government is initiation a lot of new programs in the country which are appropriate to people’s society to bring together the objective of the country’s growth. As the e-banking services contain started successfully in the Tirunelveli city in the past few years, the banking sectors have to convene the competition among the banking sector. Every year the electronic deliverance of banking services is attractive the perfect technique for the banks to convene their customer's prospect.

Objectives of the Study

- To estimate, analyze and measure up to the opinions and satisfaction level of E-banking services in selected banks in Tirunelveli.
- To value and evaluate the problems faced by the customers of public and private sector banks in utilizing e-banking services
- To offer and suggestions to recover the e-banking customer services.

Research Methodology

Research design	The research design adopted in the study was a descriptive design
Area of study	The area of the study is in Tirunelveli City
Period of study	The study was conducted for two months
Source of Data	The study is collected both primary and secondary data
Sampling Design	The sampling design is convenient random sampling. The total number of samples is 120.
Tools for analysis	The collected data was analyzed with the help of a percentage table and five-point Likert scale

Limitations of the Study

The study is limited to the customers’ perspective. Therefore it does not coat any performance appraisal or estimation on e-banking services from bankers’ viewpoint.

Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1.1
Demographic profile of the respondents

S. No.	Particulars	Classification	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Gender	Male	78	65
		Female	42	35
2.	Age	Below 25 years	18	15
		Above 26 - 35	46	38.33
		Above 36 - 45	38	31.67
		More than 45 years	18	15
3.	Educational Qualification	School level	10	8.33
		ITI / Diploma	18	15
		Graduate	40	33.33
		Post Graduate	28	23.33
		Professional	24	20
4.	Monthly Income	Below Rs. 10,000	10	8.33
		Rs. 10,001 – 15,000	28	23.33
		Rs. 15,001 – 20,000	38	31.67
		Rs. 20001 – 25,000	19	15.83
		Above 25,000	25	20.83
5.	Average monthly transaction	Below Rs. 10,000	27	22.5
		Rs. 10,001 – 15,000	22	18.33
		Rs. 15,001 – 20,000	35	29.17
		Rs. 20,001 – 25,000	26	21.67
		Above Rs. 25000	10	8.33

Interpretation

In the above table, it is indicated that 65 % of the respondents are male and 35 % of the respondents are female. Out of the total respondents, 15 % of the respondents are 25 years old and below. 38.33 % of the respondents age between 26 -35, 31.67 % of the respondents belong to the age group between 36 – 45, and 15 % of the respondents are above 45 years of age. Out of the total respondents, 31.33 and 23.33 % of the respondents are graduates and postgraduates correspondingly. 23.33 % of the respondents are in the income level between Rs. 10001 -15,000. In this group, 20.83 % of the respondent's income level is above Rs. 25,000. 29.17 % of the respondents spend Rs 15,001 – 20,000 of their monthly e-banking transactions Only 8.33 of the respondents spend more than Rs. 25,000 for their e-banking transactions.

Table 1.2
Frequency of using E-Banking services

S. No.	Services	Particulars	No. of respondents	Percentages
1.	Money transfer	One	20	16.67
		Two	32	26.67
		Three	35	29.17
		Four	20	16.67
		Five & Above	13	10.83
2	Payment of E.B bill/ Telephone bill	One	36	30
		Two	28	23.33
		Three	30	25
		Four	16	13.33
		Five & Above	10	8.33
3	Mobile Recharge	One	38	31.67
		Two	28	23.33
		Three	24	20
		Four	20	16.67
		Five & Above	10	8.33
4	Air/ Railway Ticket Booking	One	24	20
		Two	38	31.67
		Three	26	21.67
		Four	18	15
		Five & Above	14	11.67
5	Online shopping	One	12	10
		Two	28	23.33
		Three	37	30.83
		Four	25	20.83
		Five & Above	18	15

The above table indicates, Out of the total respondents, 29.17 percent of respondents are using the e-banking services three times for money transfers. Among the total respondents taken for analysis, 30 percent of the respondents used e-banking services to pay the electricity bill and telephone bills once in 3 months. Out of the total respondents using the e-banking services a maximum of 31.67 of the respondents is using the e-banking services for mobile recharge one time in three months time. Out of the total respondents using the e-banking services a maximum of 31.67 of the respondents is using the e-banking services for Air ticket/ railway ticket booking two times in three months time. Out of the total respondents using the e-banking services, a maximum of 30.83 of the respondents are using the e-banking services for online shopping three times in three months time

Table 1.3
Customer satisfaction regarding E-banking services

No	Factors	Respondent's Response					Likert Scale		
		SA	A	No idea	DA	SDA	Weighted score	Total Score	Percentile Points
1.	Appropriate and accurate information	28	36	13	20	23	386	600	64.33
2.	Efficient information	35	27	25	18	15	409	600	68.17
3.	Connects without delay to bank accounts	28	40	12	21	19	297	600	49.5
4.	Immediate facilitate for problems or query	28	38	18	17	19	399	600	66.5
5.	Secure in providing individual information	32	38	18	20	12	418	600	69.67
6.	Safe with online transaction	40	35	15	20	10	435	600	72.5
7.	Service systems are easy to use	26	42	15	19	18	441	600	73.5
8.	Systems are clear and understandable	30	28	20	16	26	380	600	63.33
9.	Available all 365 days / 24 hours	32	44	16	18	10	430	600	71.67
10.	Uniform services	26	32	28	18	16	394	600	65.67

As per the above calculation, a total of 73.5 percentile better overall process of Service systems are easy to use. Safe with the online transaction is also fine with 58.33 percentile points, followed by Available all 365 days/ 24 hours

Suggestions

- Banks should make their internet banking services client-friendly with simple process systems.
- Increasing more number of ATM networks in Tirunelveli city.
- Customers should be made educated about the use of e-banking products and services.

Conclusion

E-banking is a borderless mortal permit anytime and anyway banking. This facility us through all the functions and a bundle of benefits as compared to conventional banking services. In India, E-banking is day by day upward. No doubt Indian banks are making genuine hard work for the acceptance of highly developed technology and fitting of e-delivery channels but silent masses are cautious of the perception. Banks are creation genuine efforts to develop the e-banking products and services.

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